

CULTURAL HERITAGE OF ANCIENT UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction.

The cultural heritage formed in ancient Uzbekistan is an integral part of human history, and with its uniqueness, diversity and richness, it has made a great contribution to the development of world culture. Historically and culturally, the territory of Uzbekistan has embodied cultural monuments and heritages of various peoples and civilizations since ancient times. Peoples, different religions and civilizations have been in contact with each other here for thousands of years, creating unique examples of art and culture. Architectural monuments, crafts, musical art, folklore, literature and other cultural aspects constitute the historical and cultural identity of the Uzbek people.

The cultural heritage of ancient Uzbekistan is of great importance not only in the study of its history, but also in the formation of modern culture. These cultural heritages reflect not only the uniqueness of the Uzbek people, but also the mutual relations between the cultures of Central Asia and the world. Today, the study and preservation of the cultural heritage of ancient Uzbekistan is of great importance not only for scientific research, but also for promoting the cultural wealth of the world community.

This thesis analyzes the cultural heritage of ancient Uzbekistan, its components and its contribution to world culture. Also, the role and importance of this heritage in modern society and scientific and practical approaches to its preservation are considered.

In the center of Ichan-Kala stands one of the tallest minarets in Uzbekistan. This is the minaret of Islam Khoja. The minaret is part of the same complex, which includes a madrasa and a mosque. The height of the minaret is 56.6 meters and it is the second largest in Central Asia. The first place in height is the Qutlug Temur minaret in Old Urgench (height 62 meters), and the third place is the Khasti Imam minaret in Tashkent (height 53 meters).

The construction of the minaret began in 1908 at the initiative of the chief minister of the Khiva khans Muhammad Rahim Khan and Asfandiyar Khan - Islam Khoja. The construction was attended by the best Central Asian architects

of that time, among them Khudoybergan Haji and famous naqqoshi Eshmuhammad Khudoyberdiev and Bolta Voisov.

Photo 1. Tower of Islam Khoja.

At the base, the diameter of the minaret is 9.5 meters, which is traditionally narrowed to the top. When you look at the minaret from below upwards, you can feel the grandeur of this structure. The top of the minaret is decorated with a lace cornice, illuminated by a small dome lamp above the preacher's room. The base of the minaret is made of burnt brick. The brickwork is laid in combination with glazed bricks made of flour. The inside of the tower is a spiral staircase made of burnt brick. After going 175 steps down the stairs you can go to the main rotunda with the windows. From here there is an amazing view of the city.

Previously, the minaret was used as an observation post and to call Muslims to prayer (azan). Today, the functions of the minaret have not changed. Going up to the viewing platform, you can observe the fabulous sights of the city and hear the muezzin singing azan in prayer hours. The unique minaret of Islam Khoja is included in the UNESCO World Heritage Representative List.

You can see the grandiose complex, madrasah, minaret and khanaka in the old part of the city of Andijan. The buildings of the complex attract with their size, which are considered one of the largest in Central Asia and magnificent traditional decor. The surface of the minaret is decorated with an ornament in the form of a medallion, inside of which sayings from the Koran are embossed in Arabic.

Photo 1. Madrasah and tower in Andijan.

In the past centuries, muddaris (teachers of theological schools) and imams were trained in the complex, now there is a Museum of Literature and Art of the Andijan region, where you can learn about the culture and history of the region.

Conclusion.

The cultural heritage of ancient Uzbekistan, as an integral part of human history, played an important role in the development of not only the Uzbek people, but also the entire Central Asian and world culture. Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage reflects the life, ways of thinking and aesthetic views of ancient peoples through its unique architectural monuments, art, literature, music and handicrafts. These heritages have not lost their importance not only in the historical, but also in the formation of modern culture.

Today, the issues of studying and preserving the cultural heritage of ancient Uzbekistan are of urgent importance. Preservation and promotion of this heritage creates great opportunities not only in scientific research, but also in the fields of cultural tourism, education and international relations. The role and importance of ancient monuments and works of art in modern society plays an important role in uniting society and strengthening ties between the past and the present.

At the same time, the need to preserve the ancient cultural heritage, to pass it on to future generations, as well as to widely promote its importance at the

international level, is increasing day by day. Protecting cultural heritage and analyzing it on a scientific basis allows for a deeper understanding of not only its historical significance, but also its role in today's society. Scientific and practical work in this regard will provide opportunities to further enrich our culture and promote it in the international arena

References:

1. Ismailov, T. (2022, November). THE FORT THAT SPEAKS FROM THE PAST. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 18-22).
2. Ismailov, T. (2024). PALACE OF THE KHOREZMSHAKH. Models and methods in modern science, 3(3), 5-7.
3. Ismailov, T. (2024). KO'HNA VA HAMISHA NAVQIRON SHAHAR. Молодые ученые, 2(2), 71-72.
4. Ismailov, T. (2023). EMBOSSSED KHIVA PILLARS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(4), 63-66.
5. Ismailov, T. (2024). MONUMENTS OF ANCIENT KHOREZM. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(4), 175-176.
6. Ismailov, T. (2024). SULTON UVAYS ZIYORATGOHI. Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 3(4), 46-47.
7. Ismailov, T. (2024). QADIMGI XORAZM YODGORLIKLARI-TUPROQQAL'A. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 3(4), 104-105.
8. Ismailov, T. (2024). THE LIGHT FROM THE SHOVIOT. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 9-13.
9. Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2023). Hazrati Pahlavon Mahmud maqbarasi. Science and Education, 4(3), 106-113.
10. Ismailov, T. (2024). "ULLI-KHOVLI" CULTURAL COMPLEX. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 10, сс. 76-78). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13999651>